

Reactions of Dichlorobis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) and -zirconium(IV) with Tetradentate Schiff Bases derived from Hydroxyaldehydes and Phenylenediamine

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Dichlorobis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) and -zirconium(IV), [η^5 -C₅H₅]₂TiCl₂ and [η^5 -C₅H₅]₂ZrCl₂, react with tetradentate Schiff bases such as salicydene-*o*-phenylenediamine, salicydene-*p*-phenylenediamine, 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde-*o*-phenylenediamine, 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde-*p*-phenylenediamine, in 1 : 1 molar ratio in refluxing tetrahydrofuran at 66° in presence of triethylamine (used as scavenging agent) to yield complexes of the type (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂Ti(SB) and (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂Zr(SB) respectively, where SB is the anion of the corresponding Schiff base, SBH₂. The complex derivatives have been characterised on the basis of their conductance measurements and spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and electronic) studies.

The field of Schiff base complexes is fast developing on account of wide variety of structures possible for ligands depending upon aldehydes and amines¹⁻³. Schiff bases derived from the reaction of salicylaldehyde with primary amines⁴ and 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde with the primary amines⁵ represent a versatile series of ligands, metal complexes of which have been widely studied⁴⁻⁹. Various Schiff base complexes of

bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) and bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) with bidentate, terdentate and tetradentate Schiff base have been reported¹⁰⁻¹⁶. Transition metal Schiff base complexes of metallocenes are important on account of their industrial application as catalysts for polymerisation^{17,18} and hydrogenation¹⁹ of unsaturated hydrocarbons.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Yield %	Conductance $M \times 10 = 0.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				Ti/Zr	N
1.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Ti (<i>N,N</i> -bis(salicydene)- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine)	70	0.23	8.78 (8.86)	5.23
2.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Ti (<i>N,N</i> -bis(salicydene)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine)	75	0.25	8.75 (8.85)	5.06 (5.53)
3.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Ti (<i>N,N</i> -bis(2-hydroxy-naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde)- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine)	68	0.22	8.76 (8.83)	5.08 (5.54)
4.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Ti (<i>N,N</i> -bis(2-hydroxy-naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine)	65	0.26	8.67 (8.77)	4.80 (5.03)
5.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Zr (<i>N,N</i> -bis(salicydene)- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine)	74	0.24	15.44 (15.22)	4.96 (5.52)
6.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Zr (<i>N,N</i> -bis(salicydene)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine)	67	0.22	15.54 (15.63)	4.92 (5.35)
7.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Zr (<i>N,N</i> -bis(2-hydroxy-naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde)- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine)	71	0.25	14.88 (15.65)	5.08 (5.33)
8.	(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Zr (<i>N,N</i> -bis(2-hydroxy-naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine)	70	0.27	15.49 (15.65)	5.06 (5.25)

TABLE 2-IR, ¹H NMR AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl no*	$\nu_{\max}(\text{cm}^{-1})$						$\delta(\text{ppm})$			$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$		
	(C-H)	(C-C)	i.p(C-H)	o.p(C-H)	(IC=N)	(C-O)	C ₆ H ₅	-CH=N-	Aromatic ring protons	(Benzoid)	(-CH=N)	(CH=N-)
1	3 080	1 450	1 020	805	1 600	1 295	6 42	8 65	6.70-7.60	254	322	372
2.	3 080	1 440	1 020	8.0	1 605	1 300	6 30	8.60	6.75-7.70	250	320	378
3.	3 090	1 439	1 025	815	1 610	1 290	6.40	8 68	6.80-7.62	252	326	380
4	3 085	1 445	1 025	810	1 605	1 295	6.38	8.70	6.72-7.60	250	324	378
5	3 080	1 450	1 020	805	1 610	1 300	6 32	8.65	6.78-7.65	255	320	375
6	3 085	1 440	1 020	815	1 610	1 295	6.40	8.62	6.70-7.62	254	326	373
7	3 090	1 441	1 020	810	1 605	1 295	6.35	8 60	6.78-7.60	252	325	378
8.	3 080	1 445	1 025	815	1 619	1 290	6.42	8.66	6.75-7.65	255	320	375

*Refers to corresponding compound in Table 1.

The present work describes the reaction of Schiff base formation and the reaction involved in the complexation of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{MCl}_2$ with the tetradentate Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthlene-1carbaldehyde, with *o*- and *p*-phenylenediamine, where M = Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV}.

Results and Discussion

Dichlorobis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)-M^{IV}Cl₂ (where M = Ti^{IV}) or Zr^{IV} react in presence of triethylamine with quadridentate Schiff bases of the type [X(OH)CHN-R-NCH(OH)X] and represented as SBH₂ (where X = C₆H₄ or C₁₀H₆; R = 1,2-C₄H₄ or 3,6-C₄H₄ moieties of phenylenediamine) in 1 : 1 molar ratio, to form the complexes of the type $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{M}(\text{SB})$ as per equation,

where (SB)²⁻ represents anion of the corresponding tetradentate Schiff bases SBH₂.

Analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The reaction involved in the Schiff base formation is

where R is *para*-phenylene or *ortho*-phenylene moiety, and X is salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-carbaldehyde moiety.

Ir spectra : The assignment of characteristic infrared frequencies for $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{SB})$ and the complexes are listed in Table 2. Absorption bands indicating the presence of the cyclopentadienyl groups are found at ca 3 080 $\nu(\text{C-H})$, 1 450 $\nu(\text{C-C})$ and 805 $\delta_{\text{op}}(\text{C-H})$ and 1 020 cm^{-1} $\delta_{\text{ip}}(\text{C-H})$. Appearance of these frequencies in these Schiff base derivatives confirms the delocalisation of electrons in the cyclopentadienyl ring. It is further supported by breathing mode of band at ~1 160 cm^{-1} and the band at ca (~440 cm^{-1}) which may be assigned to the metal-ring stretching frequencies²¹.

In the spectra of the complexes a strong band is observed at ca 1 625 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the azomethine $\nu(\text{-HC=N-})$ group, characterising the coordination of nitrogen to the metal atom because this frequency is observed at ca ~1 620 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the Schiff base complexes¹⁰⁻¹³. The lowering of this band in the complexes is due to decline in the electron density in the azomethine linkage. A high intensity band is observed at ca 1 295 cm^{-1} in the Schiff bases which can be assigned at ca 1 315 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes. Shifting of this band to the higher

the metal through oxygen. It is further supported by disappearance or broad OH band at 3 300–3 150 cm^{-1} of the complexes. Bands at 570–540 and 525–425 cm^{-1} are attributed to the (Ti–O), (Zr–O) and (Ti–N), (Zr–N) vibrations respectively.

^1H nrm spectra : Proton magnetic resonance spectral data are listed in Table 2. The resonance signal for azomethine proton is observed at $\delta \sim 8.64$ in the spectra of the complexes while the azomethine proton is shifted downfield at $\delta \sim 8.46$ ppm in spectra of the free ligand, showing the coordination of nitrogen of azomethine group to titanium. Aromatic protons in the form of multiplet at $\delta 6.75$ – 7.68 also show the downfield shift as compared to the corresponding Schiff base (observed at $\delta 6.60$ – 7.30). This downfield Schiff supports the coordination of nitrogen of Schiff base to the metal. The phenolic OH proton signals do not appear in the Schiff base complexes on account of deprotonation and involvement of oxygen for the bond formation with the metal^{4,6}.

Electronic spectra : In the uv spectra (MeOH) of the complexes, the bands at 250, 320 and 385 nm are assigned to π – π^* (benzoid), π – π^* (azomethine) and n – π^* (azomethine) transitions respectively. In the spectra of the free ligand (Schiff bases) the position of π – π^* (azomethine) transition was observed at ~ 420 nm, while the n – π^* (benzoid) and n – π^* (azomethine) transitions were observed at the same positions. The hypsochromic shift in the Schiff base complexes may be on account of lone-pair of electrons donation by nitrogen of azomethine group to the metal atom¹¹.

The visible spectra (CHCl_3) of the complexes exhibit a single band in the 24 900–24 300 cm^{-1} region which may be assigned for charge transfer band. The absence of d – d transition rules out the presence of an unpaired electron in the Ti and Zr ions, corresponds to the electronic $(n-1)d^0, ns^0$ configuration²⁴.

Conclusion : Physicochemical studies carried out for these complexes show the coordination of ligand to the central metal atom through nitrogen of azomethine group and oxygen of phenolic group. On the basis of the studies the following

coordination may be assigned to the $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{M}(\text{SB})$ complexes.

Finally, the tentative structure of the $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{M}(\text{SB})$ complexes can be given as

where $\text{M} = \text{Ti}(\text{IV}); \text{Zr}(\text{IV})$

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ and bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ were prepared by the reaction of sodium cyclopentadiene suspension and titanium tetrachloride or zirconium tetrachloride in 2 : 1 molar ratio in tetrahydrofuran. THF was dried over sodium wire and then refluxed until it gave a blue colouration with Ph_2CO . It was finally dried by distillation from LiAlH_4 . Hexane was dried by refluxing over sodium wire followed by distillation.

Benzene and amine was fried as reported²¹. Nitrobenzene for conductance measurements was purified by the reported method²².

Titanium and zirconium were determined gravimetrically as their oxides whereas halogens were estimated as silver halides. Nitrogen was estimated by a standard method²³.

Conductance measurement was made in nitrobenzene at 30.05° using and Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra at ambient temperature (30°) at a sweep width of 900 Hz on a Higachi-R 600 F-7 spectrometer, chemical shifts being expressed relative to an internal reference of TMS (1% by volume) and electronic spectra (acetone) on a Shimadzu 431 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Schiff base : To a solution of an appropriate amine (0.10 mol) in freshly distilled ethanol (100 ml), the desired aldehyde (0.20 mol) in the same volume of freshly distilled ethanol was added dropwise with vigorous stirring. There was immediate precipitation of the products. The mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h then cooled in an ice-bath and filtered. The resulting solid was recrystallised from hot ethanol, then washed with sodium-dried diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Preparation of complexes : All the operations were carried out under thorough anhydrous conditions. The Schiff base and (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂ or (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂ZrTiCl₂ were taken in 1 : 1 molar ratio in THF in presence of Et₃N and the mixture was refluxed for 10–12 h, then fine white product of Et₃N.HCl was separated and removed by filtration. The product was extracted from solution with n-hexane under reduced pressure at room temperature.

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